

STYLISTIC ASPECTS OF COMPOUND SENTENCES

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***Annotation:** In this thesis, the scientific text is considered within the framework of its functional and stylistic features, its functional and stylistic characteristics are identified in relation to a complex sentence as a text construct as a whole, the syntactic features of a complex sentence are studied, as well as modern approaches to the translation of a complex sentence, taking into account the corresponding syntactic transformations.*

***Keywords:** Complex, compound, sentence, element, text, stylistic, feature.*

A complex sentence, being an obligatory element of a scientific text, combines various hierarchically constructed segments of the English syntax, which must be learned and correctly used in the process of translating complex sentences from English into Uzbek. A complex sentence includes not only structural elements, such as nominative-predicative parts as constituent segments of a single complex syntactic formation, it also contains a complex semantic load that the translator needs to convey as fully as possible.

An important influence on the lexico-semantic content of a complex sentence is its syntactic structure. Structural-component units of a sentence with a complex syntax contain one important feature: the structure of a complex sentence contains components that, in their meaning and content, represent separate syntactic units with their own completely independent function.¹

¹ Lasheras B., Pohlmann C., Katsioulis C., Liberti F. European Union Security and Defence White Paper, A Proposal. Berlin: Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung International Policy Analysis Division for International Dialogue, 2010. 65 p.

In the scientific text, there is a clear trend towards the use of uniform principles for the organization of language tools. Particular importance in the characterization of scientific texts in English should be given to creative elements that can be implemented in the presentation of scientific information. It is generally accepted that a scientific text should contain objectively rigorous information, without any “other-style” inclusions.

To understand the essence of a complex sentence in a scientific text, it should be noted that it is an event or situational nominations that represent the relationship between events in real life. In turn, an event or situation is a combination of participants, persons or objects connected by certain relationships, which allows us to consider complex sentences as nomination forms denoting situations that include two or more events.²

In order to describe directly the features of the translation of a complex sentence in English, as well as modern approaches to the translation of a complex sentence, we considered it necessary to dwell on the informational aspects of the translation of a complex sentence and, first of all, the basics of the formation of such information in a scientific text. When reading and subsequently translating a scientific text, it is necessary to understand the structure of scientific knowledge in general and what constitutes such knowledge at the linguo-semantic level.

The main problem in the process of transferring the syntactic structure of a complex sentence is the processing by the translator of grammatical structures that have no analogues in the target language. In the process of translation, the main task is to extract the meaning in a complex sentence and adequately convey it.

A complex sentence in a scientific text as a complex unit of translation varies depending on the ways of communication between its constituent structures, which divides a complex sentence into two main varieties: compound and complex sentences. When studying the translation aspects of the syntactic transformations of these types of sentences, it is necessary to take into account, first of all, the structural

² Kaushanskaya V.Z. and other «A grammar of the English» Leningrad 1971.310p

features of these types of sentences, which is expressed in the pluralism of approaches regarding the essence of a complex sentence as a complex syntactic unit.

The syntactic complexity of a complex sentence as a unit of translation is expressed by a polypredicative connection, which is realized through the punctuation differentiation of its component predicative parts. In the study of the structural syntax of an English compound sentence, there is a plurality of approaches.

When analyzing the translation of complex sentences in a scientific text, we used the following syntactic transformations: segmentation and union of sentences, replacement of members of sentences, replacement of the type of sentences. Such transformations were applied by us taking into account the semantic coherence of the informative field of the English compound sentence.

The lexico-semantic content of the scientific text required the use of complex syntactic units overloaded with information, which created certain difficulties in translation. One of the basic problems of translating a complex sentence in a scientific text is the selection of the necessary syntactic construction that would most fully correspond to the semantic content of an equivalent syntactic unit.³

Thus, as a unit of translation, a complex sentence is subject to translation transformations, among which there are various approaches to the ways of transforming its syntactic structure in English. It is necessary to take into account the degree of informativeness of a complex sentence in any approach to its translation from English into Uzbek. First of all, this is manifested in endowing a complex sentence with such a universal, extralinguistic quality as an informative value, since with such an interpretation of the function of a complex sentence in the linguistic communicative space, i.e. the ability to include in its syntactic structure certain meanings embedded in the lexical “palette” of the information chain of a complex sentence, the method of translation transformations at the level of syntax may differ.

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³ Ganshina M.A. Vasilevskaya N.M. «English grammar» M., Higher school publishing house 1964 127 p.

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